

COVID^X

COVID eXponential Programme

GRANT AGREEMENT ID: 101016065

FAQ - THE COVID-X SANDBOX

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Here you can find a list of the most common questions about the sandbox:

1. When are we going to be able to use the sandbox?
First version of the sandbox will be released by the end of April. We will make a general announcement as soon as we have it ready.
2. What kind of functionalities will provide the sandbox?
Main functionalities to be provided are related to the access, visualization and ingestion of clinical data. We will also provide different tools for allowing the deployment of software solutions within the platform in order to run your own models, following a CI/CD approach. These software solutions should be dockerized.
3. How can we use the sandbox?
It depends on your specific solution. The sandbox is a common tool and a mandatory requirement for the deployed containers to access clinical data, so you have to decide how this can help you in the provision of your solution.
4. Who can use the sandbox?
The sandbox will be available for the team members and also for the single solution partners. It will be deployed on the clinical premises in case the 3rd party healthcare providers do not give their consent to move their anonymized data to the cloud-based deployment, so these partners should assure the availability and the minimum computational capabilities needed to do so.
5. What kind of data will be available in the sandbox?
Each instance of the sandbox will include the clinical data from the related clinical partner. It will also include some open data previously selected according to their relation to the different challenges. It will also store any other data the partners decide to ingest, following a specific structure (the one already in the platform or a new one provided by the team). The data model will be ready together with the platform.
6. Are we able to store data in the sandbox?
Yes, you are. A specific API will allow you to ingest the data into the sandbox, then the harmonization and management module will take care of including them in the ElasticSearch structure.
7. Will the stored data be private or public?
We follow a role-based access control, so your data will be accessible only to the members of your choice.
8. Storage and computational power are free in the sandbox?
Multimedia data are not going to be ingested in the platform, just the metadata and url. Other type of data can be annotated and stored if allowed
9. How are the issues in the server going to be managed?

The system is designed with fault tolerance in mind. Moreover, there will be a support team helping with the deployment of the sandbox. Nevertheless, since this is not a commercial project, we cannot support 24/7, just only during working days.

10. How long will the sandbox last?

As long as the project lasts. It can last longer if the platform finally goes commercial.

11. How much time do we have to make the integration with the sandbox?

This integration should be finished by the end of the third month (July 2021).

12. Are you going to prepare any technical webinar to provide more details?

Yes, we are preparing three specific webinars:

- Data visualization using Kibana
- Dockerization for software ingestion.
- CI/CD services

Dates will be previously announced.

13. How can you help us in the integration process:

We have identified three main steps:

- Information gathering: this initial phase will help us understand more about your solution and needs. We will obtain the info from your proposal and also from the initial form.
- Integration requirements definition: this phase will translate the information obtained in the previous one into the different requirements for the integration.
- Integration process: this is the main phase, when the teams and single solutions will be able to make the integration according to the initial requirements.
- Issue solving: the integration process will be continuously monitored in order to detect any specific issues and try to solve them as soon as possible.

As you know, the technical contact point is Silvia Uribe (UPM): sum@gatv.ssr.upm.es.